

THE ROLE OF GRAMMAR IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract: This article explains about English grammar and its importance. English grammar is the main part because first of all in learning a foreign language, letters are learned, then grammar is learned, and then speaking, writing, and listening comprehension are progressed. Grammar plays an important role in speaking skills to speak correctly without mistakes.

Keywords: grammar, pedagogical communication, upper classes, innovative methods.

INTRODUCTION

A person who comes across the term "grammar" while reading or listening to someone else's speech can understand it in different ways. There is a reason for this. "Grammar" in the mother tongue course in high school is understood as a field, a branch of linguistics. When studying a foreign language, it is considered the grammatical aspect of speech. Applying the various information stated in scientific sources for the purpose of foreign language teaching, the word "grammar" can be limited to two concepts: 1) the grammatical side of speech - the grammatical events of the language that occur in speaking, listening, reading and writing (e.g. speech pattern; personal form of the verb; article) 2) abstract nouns representing linguistic phenomena (e.g. the possessive takes the first place in the sentence; the plural suffix is added to the singular form of the noun).

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

The methodology of foreign language teaching as a science has more than 200 years of history. During this period, it can be observed that different attitudes towards foreign language teaching methodology were expressed. One of these views belongs to academician L. V. Shcherba. In his opinion, although the teaching methodology of any subject is a science, it is not considered a theoretical science. It solves practical problems. The most valuable books on methodology are also written by linguists. These include G. Suit, one of the phonetists of the 19th century and a great English linguist, O. Yesperson, who is considered the most original phonetist and theoretical linguist in England at the end of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th century. At the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, a number of personal qualities necessary for the most prominent pedagogical communication culture - honesty, openness, self-control, demandingness, sincerity, patience, endurance, tactics, etc. includes. The next task in preparing the language material for the educational process is to distribute the selected minimum. It is known that the meaning, application and construction of the grammatical event was taken as the unit of selection (the meaning is primary in the formation of speech, and the form is primary in perception). Expressing grammatical meaning: morphemes (prefix, suffix; suffix; form without root word); auxiliary words (auxiliary verb; article; preposition; conjunction; pronoun; verbs whose meaning is completely or partially lost (desemanticized), etc.); verbs in sentences and combinations z order; syntactic phonetics phenomena.

The distribution of grammatical material requires a functional (that is, according to its function in speech) approach. The selection unit of grammar is a completely separate methodological concept, the construction, meaning and application of a grammatical event is considered a separate unit, even the concepts of micro-use, micro-meaning, and micro-form have been scientifically researched. So, micro-form, micro-meaning, micro-use are recognized as a grammatical selection unit. According to L.V. Shcherba, the concept of passive grammar includes grammatical phenomena used in perceptual understanding (reading, listening) and abstractions related to them. The term "passive" applies only to the educational material, and the need for the

student's activity to be always active in education is widely recognized in psychology and education. Students are selected from passive grammatical minimum written texts for their written speech. Grammatical phenomena reflecting the style of written speech are selected. Active and passive grammatical minimums do not have a sharp difference. Active for grades 5-7 and only passive grammatical minimum for upper grades and high schools and colleges is selected and followed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The system of teaching grammar of a foreign language includes the formation of grammatical skills, the acquisition of grammatical material and the study of generalization. These, in turn, require the implementation of exercises aimed at forming skills and mastering the material. So, exercises are a means of overcoming difficulties related to material, actions and generalizations. Below are some examples of exercises designed to teach foreign language grammar.

1. Finding the grammatical phenomenon being studied from the text being perceived.
2. Distinguish new grammar from other familiar phenomena.
3. Saying the name of the heard/read grammatical event.
4. Grammatically simple analysis of the sentence.
5. Using the grammatical event told by the student (teacher) in a sentence.
6. Systematization of grammatical material (for example, making sentences in present, past, future tenses).
7. Free use of grammatical events in a speech situation.
8. Describe the picture in the present (present, future) tense.
9. Answering questions using the appropriate grammatical event.
10. Translating sentences containing difficult grammatical events.

In fact, language learning through the student's senses is more effective and useful than other methods. Learning through listening and writing can be a bit boring, so using games and various foreign language prompts to teach students a foreign language will help the student to concentrate and become more interested in learning the language. increases.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it is advisable to teach language to students, i.e. school-aged children, not by forcing them, but by using interesting games and innovative methods, because students are always taught in interesting ways. We can focus on learning a foreign language, and at the same time, using interesting methods is very useful and should serve as a foundation for their future knowledge. Therefore, as the educational system also aims to educate free, mature, mature individuals with their own opinions, in the future, we future teachers should develop technologies for more effective use of innovative technologies. We can contribute by exiting.

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